

Co-creation and Learner Personas Applied to the Inclusive Design of a Learning Analytics Dashboard

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Abstract. This short paper reports on a small student-staff partnership and co-creation project, which uses a participatory design approach and learner personas for the inclusive design of a learning analytics dashboard. The objective is to involve learners throughout the design process to help prevent instructors' biases ending up in the design of the dashboard. We discuss how small (and not so inclusive) student-staff partnerships have the potential to effectively help instructional designers be more inclusive of diverse learners' needs, priorities, experiences, behaviours, goals and circumstances.

Keywords: Inclusivity · Co-creation · Participatory design · Personas.

1 Introduction

Inclusion in education implies that all learners can access and gain equal opportunities to learning. Successful inclusive education attends to physical, cognitive, academic, social, and emotional learners' differences. Unfortunately, negative, exclusionary, and discriminatory learner experiences can come in many forms, be it denied access, identity demeaning or frustrating experiences [1]. When approaching educational technology design, one should proactively seek out points of exclusion and use them to create inclusive solutions.

Following WCAG (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines) can help designing for a diverse range of abilities. But beyond their ability, learners might be excluded across a spectrum of permanent, temporary, and situational scenarios. Differing from ability-based exclusion, situational exclusion describes situations where a learner is temporarily unable to access or use learning resources effectively. Offering various ways to engage is a key principle of inclusive design. For example, giving learners different options allow them to choose the method that best suits their unique circumstances and needs. However, when designing different ways for learners to engage, all learner experiences should be comparable.

Another key principle to inclusive design is to avoid unintended personal biases ending up in the instructional design. In this short paper we briefly report on a co-creation project, which uses a participatory design approach and learner

personas for the inclusive design of a Learning Analytics Dashboard (LAD). The objective is to involve learners throughout the design process to help prevent instructors' biases ending up in the design of the dashboard. We discuss how small (and not so inclusive) student-staff partnerships have the potential to effectively help instructional designers be more inclusive of diverse learners' needs, priorities, experiences, behaviours, goals and circumstances.

2 Participatory Design

Participatory Design is a user-centered approach to design that invites all stakeholders into the design process as a means of better understanding, meeting, and sometimes preempting their needs. In participatory design, participants are invited to cooperate with designers, researchers, and developers during an innovation process, not only through decision making but also idea generation. Participatory design's paradigm is constructivist as it sees knowledge making as occurring through the interaction among people, practices, and artifacts [2]. The goal of participatory design is to create solutions that better meet the needs and expectations of the people who will use them.

Participatory design (or co-creation) of educational technology involves learners working alongside designers to create prototypes and provide feedback on design concepts. The design process typically involves three stages [3]: stage 1 is an 'initial exploration of the work' to gain an understanding of the learning context; stage 2 is a 'discovery process', which is the most interactive stage, involving techniques such as brainstorming, mind mapping, personas, and storyboarding; and stage 3 is the 'prototyping' of the learning resource or technology.

The benefits of participatory design are numerous. Beside preventing personal biases ending up in the instructional design, instructors can gain a deeper understanding of learners' needs, preferences, and experiences. This leads to more effective and adapted solutions. Participatory design can also help to identify potential issues early on in the design process, before they become more difficult to fix. Finally, involving learners in the design process can help build trust and create a sense of ownership.

3 Learner Personas and Persona Spectrum

Learner personas are fictional characters, which represent the different learner types that might use an educational resource or technology. Creating personas can help build empathy with learners and gain a perspective similar to theirs. Personas should always be created from observations about real learners, and never be invented out of assumptions about them.

A persona spectrum goes further by taking a "typical" learner and create iterations of that same persona across a spectrum of abilities, identities, backgrounds, or experiences to factor a wider range of needs. For example, one persona could be having limited use of one arm permanently (amputation or paral-

ysis), temporarily (arm is in a cast), or situationally (they're holding a cup of coffee or a child) [4].

4 Co-creation of a LAD Using Personas

4.1 Learner-facing LAD

Learner-facing LAD (i.e., systems that track learning analytics data and report it directly to students) are becoming increasingly available [5]. They enable students to understand how their learning is progressing, promote critical reflection skills and can also help students improve their Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) skills [6]. However, “their development has outpaced our understanding of effective design and how these tools do-or do not-support learning” [7]. The aim of our co-creation project is to propose novel and inclusive designs of learner-facing LADs.

4.2 Context

The course used in the project is a course on Multimedia Fundamentals taught to approximately 240 undergraduate students enrolled on a transnational programme on Telecommunications Engineering in China. The course proposes on the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) a variety of digital learning activities and resources. They consist in reading materials, short interactive videos, quizzes and exercise worksheets. Each week, prior to attending a synchronous tutorial, students are asked to have completed all exercises embedded in the interactive videos, attempted the quiz and completed the worksheet covering the topic of the week. However, the learning is mostly self-regulated.

The course adopts the flipped classroom model. Flipping the classroom requires from students good SRL skills, as they must have engaged in learning activities prior to attending tutorials. Students' SRL skills needed for successful flipped learning primarily include organisation, time management, and effort regulation. A student-facing LAD that can provide clues to students about their time management and effort regularity can thus be very useful.

During the 2022 delivery of the course, a total of 65 digital learning activities were proposed for which time-stamped digital traces were collected daily (timing of the engagement with each activity, and scores obtained). Learning analytics conducted using this data have revealed interesting insights into various students learning behaviours [8].

4.3 Design Process of the LAD

Six students currently enrolled on the course were recruited as unpaid participants. Together with one final year student, responsible for the implementation of the LAD prototype, and the course lecturer, they made up the participatory design team. Eight two-and-a-half-hour participatory design sessions (20 hours in total) were conducted, some online, some face-to-face.

Fig. 2. Ya Lin's persona.

dents and create learner personas (see Fig. 1). They covered the following main aspects: goals, motivation, skills, attitude, and circumstances (e.g., quality of personal equipment and study space). The design participants were then asked to think about their friends and classmates and to precisely describe them using these characteristics. Two examples of resulting personas are shown in Fig 2 and Fig 3.

Ya Lin's main goal (Fig. 2) is to be recommended for post-graduate studies, and for this, she needs to achieve good grades on the course. She has suitable personal equipment (i.e., good internet connection and personal computer) and

Fig. 3. Zhang Wei's persona.

has plenty of time to engage in her studies as she is not committed to a part-time job. She tends to go to the library for studying. She has good time management skills. However, she suffers from stress and anxiety, and she finds it difficult to keep concentrated on her studies. The LAD should help her focus on what is important to succeed, keep track of her achievements and give messages of encouragement.

Compared to Ya Lin, Zhang Wei's goal (Fig. 3) is simply to graduate and to find a job. He is already working part-time. He tends to study at night in his shared dormitory room. His personal equipment is of poor quality (slow network connection). He often feels sad and tired. The LAD should help him manage his time and motivate him to engage more with the VLE's learning activities.

5 Results and Discussion

Fig. 4. LAD lo-fi prototypes.

Fig. 5. LAD first functional prototype.

Six learner personas were produced to cover as completely as possible the wide spectrum of students' abilities, skills, goals and circumstances, as defined

and reported by the design participants. For each persona, a scenario, a storyboard and ideas about what the LAD should contain, what functions it should provide, how it should behave and be interacted with, were then discussed. Some resulting drawings of lo-fi prototypes are shown in Fig. 4. Based on these, decisions were then taken collectively for the implementation of a first functional LAD (Fig. 5). It includes functions such as a calendar, reminders, encouraging messages, simple motivational games, progress charts and graphs, etc. Students are free to use the functions that are the most useful to them. In other words, they can adapt their use of the LAD according to their own needs (later, the goal is to make the LAD automatically adaptive to various learners' profiles).

The LAD will be deployed next semester for the next cohort of students on the course and will be thoroughly evaluated then. However, a brief survey, answered by 31 current students on the course (11 identified as male and 20 identified as female), was deployed to evaluate the representativity of the personas. The respondents were asked to choose which of the six personas they felt the closest to. Each persona was chosen by at least 1 student (2 of the personas were chosen by 11 and 10 students respectively, a third one by 4 students, then 3, 2 and 1 student respectively chose one of the remaining personas).

One known concern about student-facing LADs is how to ensure regular use of the LAD over time and by all students, i.e., not only students who are already highly engaged, but also struggling or at risk of disengaging students. The participatory design approach has allowed learners and designers, not only to gain a good understanding of the learners diversity, but also to address in the most inclusive manner the concerns about student use and adoption of a learner-facing LAD.

One of the main outcomes of this small co-creation project is the understanding of how small (and not so inclusive) student-staff partnerships have the potential to effectively help instructional designers be more inclusive of diverse learners' needs, priorities, experiences, behaviours, goals and circumstances. There is a distinction to be made between inclusive partnerships and partnerships for inclusivity. The work described in this paper is an example of the later.

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